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Investigation into the Difficulties of Palestinian EFL Learners in Learning Intonation in Written and Spoken Context

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research study was to investigate the difficulties faced by the EFL (junior) learners at Islamic University of Gaza, Palestine in learning intonation in written and spoken contexts. To this end, two valid and reliable instruments were used-1) diagnostic test to measure the intonation-learning problem in written texts, and 2) the observation card to measure the intonation-learning difficulties in spoken contexts. The number of students who took diagnostic test and observation cards is 70 and 30 students respectively. Descriptive and analytic methods were used to analyze the data. The results showed that the EFL (junior) learners at Islamic University of Gaza, Palestine face various difficulties in learning intonation in written and spoken context. In addition, the students' awareness of intonation in spoken context and simple intonation pattern was better than their awareness of intonation in written test and complex intonation pattern.

Keywords: Pronunciation, Intonation, EFL Learners, Suprasegmentals features, Palestine

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1. Introduction

Generally speaking, teaching pronunciation is a very crucial characteristic of foreign language teaching, especially teaching the sounds and intonation patterns of English language at early stage of learning English. To achieve the aforementioned concepts, the good teacher, the well-designed materials, and the constant exposure to the good models and practice are required. The teachers and the students should realize the sound system of English and be aware of the phonetic problems that affect the learning process. In order to identify the mistakes and tackle them well, the teacher should employ the target sounds in the learning activities to allow students practice these sounds while they are doing the exercises. The main concern of this research is *intonation*, a main Suprasegmental feature of phonology. Wasal and Gamage (2007) have explained that the stream of speech is composed of two kinds of phonological unite: segmental sounds and Suprasegmental sounds. The segmental sounds can be divided into clear, separate unit, for example, vowels and consonants, whereas the Suprasegmental features are pitch, intonation, stress, and accent. As phonemic aspect of them gives various meaning, it is suggested that learners should learn them. It is also necessary to investigate the learners' difficulties in learning intonation and identify the learning strategies used so that some pedagogical suggestions can be made and problems and difficulties can be solved. In this regard, the present study investigates the problems faced by the Palestinian EFL learners who fail to recognize the Suprasegmental aspects of language and the instructional strategies in learning intonation. The result is, the Palestinian EFL learners mix intonation of English language into Arabic and vice versa. This may be due to lacking of strategies to

learn or teach intonation at school and university level. The paper would seek to find answers to some questions such as- what difficulties do the junior students at Islamic University of Gaza in Palestine face while learning intonation in written contexts, what are the causes of these problems and what strategies can be used to overcome these difficulties faced in learning intonation.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Intonation: Concept and Functions

Simply speaking, intonation refers to various movements in the pitch describing the levels (high/low), and tones (falling /rising) according to the context of a situation. Moreover, prominence is a very important component of intonations; according to Roach (1991:86), the prominence is to make some syllables more obvious in pronunciation. It is clear that language is a way of communicating ideas and expressing feelings in the real world and in electronic world. To do that, the speakers use intonation to express their thoughts and emotions and to achieve the qualitative and quantitative process of communication. Also, intonation adds musicality to the speech to attract the hearers.

Intonation is an integrated part in the meaning of communication. If anyone traces the roots of miscommunication and misunderstanding, intonation should not be ignored when you try to analyze the problems. According to Wennerstorm (1994), intonation may be misused by native and non-native speakers. To show the importance of intonation, Jenkins (2002:87) argued that despite the importance of the tones, mistakes of prominence can lead to the faults in communication. It's clear that some speakers apply the native intonation on the English intonation, so the meaning of communication will not be attained. Various studies have also showed the crucial role of

phonology in creating the meaning. For example, a study investigated how the speakers of American and Korean English show differences in placing the information in bursts and transitions.

Some studies have pointed out that the intonation development in the early stages of babyhood shows the interaction between the physiological and linguistic influences and it is argued that intonation is probably one of the earliest acquired language features. Lenneberg (1967) asserted that adults can communicate effectively using the foreign language, yet the intonation is not easily comprehended beyond puberty. Furthermore, he also determined a critical period for language acquisition which ends at the puberty. This period has also been defined as a biologically determined period of life when language can be acquired more easily and beyond which time language is increasingly difficult to acquire.

2.2 Intonation functions

1. Attitudinal intonation: it reflects the attitudes and emotions of the speaker, and an intonation pattern may have different meanings according to the context of the conversation. There are some factors that help us understand the meaning of the intonation, which are loudness, speed, voice quality, pitch range (narrow-wide), key (natural pitch). Facial expressions, body movements and vocal effects (laughing, crying ...). For example,

→ Thank you. = it expresses a feeling of genuine gratitude.

→ Thank you. = it sounds rather casual

2. Grammatical function: it gives us information about the grammatical structures (boundaries between clauses, the distinction between question and statement, and the different types of sentences). For example, Blum (2004) suggests that there is a rise ↗ in

"yes-no" question and a fall in "wh-" question.

3. Accentual function: it determines the placement of stress, and it is said that "intonation is carried entirely by the stressed syllables of a tone-unit". However, the word stress is independent of intonation, but the tonic syllable in the tone unit is the function of the intonation. For example,

a. I have plans to | leave. (I am planning to leave.)

b. I have | plans to leave. (I have some plans that I have to leave.)

4. Discourse intonation: it demarcates the new and old information, regulates the flow of communication, and determines the expected responses. Some researchers define intonation as a speaker's way of organizing the speech and the meaning through the discourse. Focusing attention, one of the discourse intonation functions, can be determined by the falling intonation (new information) and rising intonation (old information).

/since the last time we met /when we had that
 ↘ ↙
 huge dinner / I've been on a diet.

Also, intonational subordination is another function, and that function is activated by "dropping the pitch, increasing the speed, narrowing the range of pitch, and lowering the loudness." For example, /As I expect you've heard/they're only admitting emergency cases/

Intonation can regulate the conversational behaviour by showing the beginning/end of the speaking, turn-taking, and requiring an appropriate response.

2.3 Intonation contours

According to Kreidler (1989), the linguists use the levels approach and the contour approach to describe intonation. Regarding the levels approach, there are four

levels: Low, Mid, High, and Extra High. For example,

He's / a ling / guist.

Another thing, the contour approach employs the tone patterns to describe intonation. There are varieties of tones proposed by the researchers such- fall, rise, rise-fall, fall-rise, and level.

Autosegmental approach is another way of identifying intonation, and this approach has two elements: H (High tone) and L (Low tone). For example,

H H L %
It's time to leave (% indicates the major tone-unit boundary)

However, most of the linguists agree on three elements of intonation: high, mid, and low.

2.4 Types of English intonation patterns

a) Falling intonation patter: it is short sentences, wh-question, imperatives, exclamations and questions tags.

b) Rising intonation patters: it is in statements to encourage the listener, yes-no question, questions tags (when the speaker expects a negative reply), and incomplete sentences. This pattern is divided into two types: low-rise, and high-rise.

c) Falling-rising intonation pattern: it is used to correct other people, show differences of opinions, and to imply something else.

2.5 The analysis of pitch-patterns in intonation systems

There are two ways to analyze the intonation,

a) Tune-based analysis of intonation:

Jones (1962) and his colleagues identified two holistic tunes: tune I and tune II. Couper-Kuhlen (1986:69) argued that "Whereas in tune I the pitch of the voice *falls* to a low level at the end, in tune II the voice *rises* on any unstressed syllables that follow the last stressed syllable..."

b) Tone-based analysis of intonation

Intonation may be tackled as a linguistic behavior and can be analyzed phonologically in terms of structural and systemic perceptions, and it has a communicative message with the existence of the lexical and syntactic levels in the language. According to Laver (1994), "an intonational phrase" is another term for the phonological unit of intonational structure, and the "intonational nucleus" is the most prominent syllable in the intonational phrase. The phonological system of pitch patterns in the structure of the intonational phrase is called "the system of nuclear tones".

While prominence is a feature of intonations, Bolinger (1958) proposed "pitch-accent" to describe the intonational prominence; the pitch and the lexical stress defines the prominence.

The linguistic function of intonation has two concepts: focus and presupposition. Jackendoff (1972:230) stated that focus is the information in the sentence that is assumed by the speaker not to be shared by him and the hearer, whereas the presupposition 'denotes' "the information in the sentences that is assumed by the speaker to be shared by him and the hearer." Halliday (1963) also argued that there are three different phonological system in the intonation of English: tonality, tonicity and tone. All of these helps the speaker to identify focus and pre-supposition to the listener. First, tonality is dividing the utterance into units of intonational phrase. Second, tonicity is identifying the location of intonational nucleus. Thirdly, the nuclear tone is the pitch pattern on the intonational nucleus.

2.6 Contour interaction (CI) theories Vs tone sequence (TS) theories of intonational description

Ladd (1984: 722) discussed intonation in terms of contour approach and stated that " in

this view, the basic units of intonation (at least in the European languages) are taken to be phrase or utterance-level contours: approximate over-all shapes that are correlated with grammatical meaning like 'declarative; and 'continuation' In contrast, Ladd (1984) criticized the contour approach because it harnesses the difference between grammatical and expressive uses of intonation, oversimplifies the distinction between the neutral and contrastive patterns of intonation, and concerns with the communicative function of intonation regardless the phonological form.

Ladd (1984:421-3) argued that " ... the TS theory treats intonational tunes as sequences of simpler tonal elements or pitch accents ... The CI model assumes that the individual accent-related pitch movements are specified by a separate component, and then interact with an overall tune: the TS view assumes that those pitch movement are simply concentrated to p the tune, so that ' sentence intonation' is merely is the sum of its accent-related parts."

2.7 Intonation in Arabic and English

The Arabic intonational patterns are similar to English intonation in terms of contour and meaning. Nonetheless, the Arabic speakers employ the rising tones instead of structural markers to point to questions, suggestions and offers more than English speakers, especially in the spoken form. On the other hand, the Arabic speakers use the low-falling tones when reading aloud. Kharma & Hajjaj (1989) analyzed two differences between English and Arabic intonation:

1. Tag questions: the tag question in English vary depending on the sentences before the tag questions, whereas in Arabic there is one pattern of tag question, *أليس كذلك؟* *alysa kathalek?*. The Arabic speakers use the rising tones, while the English speakers use the

rising and falling intonation according to the agreement.

2. Calling on persons: regarding English intonations, there are two cases when you call on people. Firstly, high intonation is used when the last syllable of the names is stressed. Secondly, low intonation is used when the first syllable of the names is stressed. As for Arabic intonation, the second pattern is commonly used. Arabic intonation has the following features:

- a) More primary contours in Arabic than in English because of the more primary stress in Arabic.
- b) The tonic syllable on the whole sentence, not on only single word.
- c) The focus and prominence syllables found at every single word.
- d) The rise or high-rise tone on all words in the sentence.

2.8 Intonation as a problematic aspect of EFL learning

This section will discuss the difficulties that learners face while learning intonation.

1. English language Variety

Various obstacles hinder the foreign language learners' learning of intonation. One of them is the English language varieties. There are various English language varieties such as Irish English, American English, Canadian English, Australian English, New Zealandia English, and South African English etc. These varieties lead to the varsity in dialects, accents, and phonology and the result is difficulties for the learners to assimilate them.

2. Difficulty in distinguishing tones

Pierehumbert & Hirshberg (1990) have stated that pitch accents, phrasal tones, and boundary tones contribute to the meaning of the intonational tune. Also, there is a difficulty in teaching intonational tones as it is harder to identify tones. Hyman (2007:517-518) reported that tone is the most syntagmatic, paradigmatic, ambiguous,

abstract, arbitrary, and autosegmental. Another related problem is that the learners need much time to know that information to highlight, and what word should be stressed when they are engaging in real-time conversations; they are overwhelmed by the burden of intonation. A study also reported relatively equal prominence to items, regardless of their importance to the information structure of the discourse. Therefore, such problems of not being able to define prominence results in faults in the process of communication among non-native speakers.

3. Difficulties related to the functions of intonation

a. Linguistic form-based difficulties

Teaching the structural analysis for the learners causes a problem in teaching the intonation; a change in the meaning of the sentence is related in the change in the intonation. Ramirez Verdugo (2003) reported that the intonation systems used by the non-native speakers may affect the information structure and meaning of their messages. For example, the non-native speakers do not differentiate between the asserted and presupposed information in their communication; they use a falling tone for both the old and new information, but the native speakers use the falling tone for new information and a low rise for old information through the organization of the information. As for the lexical problems, the learner cannot place the intonational tone in the polysyllabic words.

b. Attitudinal function

It's very intricate to describe the emotional nuances. For example, it is hard to differentiate between the meaning of "detached, unemotional statement of fact" (low fall) and "routine, uncommitted comment; detached and unexcited" (mid fall). Also, Crystal (2003) has stated that a

tone has to mean something (the low fall's unemotional) or its opposite (the low fall's dramatic) according to the context, so that is very serious problem for a systematic description. He suggests that the facial expressions and gestures can help to create the meaning, but it is still difficult to systemize the description. Clearly, there is a relation between the intonation and attitude, but there are some obstacles that the learners should take in confederation, for example, the pitch range, loudness, speed, voice quality, and facial expressions that can participate in making the attitudes.

c. Accentual function

Sometimes the foreign accents in second language are spoiled by the interference of the phonological system and phonetic realization of the speaker's first language; the learners mix between the two systems of phonological accents of first language and second language. Therefore, the learners do not use the pitch accent type to define the old and new information.

d. Discoursal function

According to Hewings (1990), the learners cannot control the continuous speech because there are no intonation choices in the natural speech which is because of the cross-linguistic interference. Moreover, the speakers cannot handle the key and tone choices to create intonational paragraphs because of the limited exposure to the English environment. Learners misuse the discourse markers which are one of the features of intonation which leads to the communication breakdown in terms of illogicality.

e. Difficulties related to intonation pattern

The results of Levis' study (2002) showed that the learners found difficulty in showing the differences between L* L H% and H * L H%, especially in declaratives and wh-questions, and the learners seem to be not

able to apprehend these contours: H * H H% and L * H H% in this variety of English intonation patterns.

f. Other problems

Bradford (1992:1) suggested that the intonation patterns are planned at a deeply subconscious level. Therefore, it is very difficult to describe and analyze these patterns. Because of language transfer or interlingual factors, the first language intonation affects the second language intonation pattern according to Ueyama and Jun (1996).

3. Methodology

This section describes the methodology used in the present study.

3.1 Data collection process

The data included secondary resources, for example, books, journals, statistics and web pages in addition to the primary resources which are the two tests that were distributed to the EFL learners (junior) at IUG. Analytical method is used which, according to Brown and Rodgers (2002:117), is "a research that describes group characteristics or behaviors in numerical terms."

3.2 The population and sample size

The number of students in the survey is 49 female students and 19 male students studying *Phonetics and phonology* course at IUG, Palestine. 38 students took the diagnostic written test, whereas 30 students took observation activities.

3.3 Test Content, Validity and Reliability

A cover letter about the purpose of the study was included in the test. The questions of the test were (a) multiple choice questions, (b) underlining the tonic syllable (or/and) boundaries, (c) giving the two possible meaning, and (d) utter the appropriate intonational pattern. Written test and observation card were used to achieve the purpose of the study and the following sources formed the base for this data:

- a. Roach's (2002). *English Phonetics and Phonology: A practical course*.
- b. Gimson's (2008). *Pronouncing of English*.
- c. A university course in practical phonetics. (1992) book 2: Intonation.
- d. Interviewing the university instructors about the should-be-tested items.

To achieve the validity of the validity of the test, the test was edited and evaluated by five experts. The content validity of the test was done by two groups of expert. The first one identified whether the test covered the scope of items and to what extent these items reflect the concept of the research problem. The second group evaluated if the tools employed were valid statistically and the test was good enough to make relations between the variables. Two statistical tests were applied. The first test is the criterion-related validity (Pearson test) which measure the coefficient between each item in the question and the whole question. The second test is structure validity test (Pearson test) which measures the validity of each question and the validity of the whole test; it tests the correlation coefficient between one question and all the question of the test.

3.4 Criterion related validity (Internal consistency):

Diagnostic written test:

The internal constancy was measured by taking a random sample-five students-through testing the correlation coefficient between each item and the whole question for diagnostic written test. Correlation coefficient of all the questions was significant and it was verified that the items of these questions were consistent and valid to measure what it was set for.

Structure validity of the test:

The validity of the test was done by testing the validity of each question and the validity of the whole test. It measured the correlation coefficient between each question and all the

questions of the test that have the same level of scale.

Table: 1 shows that significant values are less than 0.05 or 0.01, so the correlation coefficient of all the fields were significant at $\alpha = 0.01$ or $\alpha = 0.05$. So it can be said that the fields are valid to be measured what it was set for to achieve the main aim of the study.

Table 1: Structure validity of the tests

Question	Diagnostic written test		Observation Activities Test	
	Pearson correlation coefficient	P-value	Pearson correlation coefficient	P-value
One	0.637	0.001	0.619	0.001
Two	0.637	0.001	0.339	0.048
Three	0.530	0.006	0.787	0.000
Four	0.789	0.000	0.611	0.001
Five	0.581	0.002	0.671	0.000

3.5 Reliability of the research

The test is reliable when it produces the same results if it is taken again under the same conditions. To this end, the half Split method and Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha to measure the reliability of the test was used.

The following table: 2 shows that the general reliability for all items equal 0.843 for (Diagnostic written test) and 0.851 for (Observation Activities test), and significant α is less than 0.05. So all the corrected correlation were significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. This implies that the test is reliable and suitable.

Table 2: Split-Half Coefficient method

Q.	Diagnostic written test			Observation Activities Test		
	Pearson-correlation	Spearman-Brown Coefficient	p-value	Pearson-correlation	Spearman-Brown Coefficient	p-value
One	0.724	0.840	0.000	0.797	0.887	0.000
Two	0.714	0.833	0.000	0.646	0.785	0.000
Three	0.695	0.821	0.000	0.659	0.795	0.000
Four	0.750	0.862	0.000	0.787	0.881	0.000
Five	0.759	0.863	0.000	0.710	0.830	0.000
Total	0.729	0.843	0.000	0.740	0.851	0.000

Table 3 shows that the general reliability for all items equal 0.882 for (Diagnostic written test) and 0.886 for (Observation Activities test). This implies that the test is reliable.

Table 3: Cronbach's Alpha for Reliability

Q.	Cronbach's Alpha (Diagnostic written test)	Cronbach's Alpha (Observation Activities test)
	0.882	0.886

One	0.8678	0.901
Two	0.8562	0.810
Three	0.8437	0.8137
Four	0.881	0.9001
Five	0.876	0.879
Total	0.882	0.886

4. Statistical Analysis

The statistical package for the social science (SPSS) was used to analyze the collected data which focused on the following:

- 1- Frequencies and percentage
- 2- Alpha-Cronbach Test for measuring reliability of the items of the test
- 3- Person correlation coefficients for measuring validity of the items of the test
- 4- Spearman-Brown Coefficient
- 5- One sample test
- 6- Independent sample test
- 7- One way ANOVA
- 8- Scheffer test for multiple comparisons

4.1 The Results of Analysis

The following results were obtained:

What difficulties do the EFL learners (junior) at IUG, Palestine face while learning intonation in written contexts?

To this, the following frequencies of responses for each item in the test were received which were calculated in terms of the mean, standard deviation, weight mean, t-value, and p-value.

Table 4: Results of all questions related to the diagnostic written test

No	Items	Mean	Standard deviation	Weight mean	t-value	p-value	rank
5	Five	3.47	0.461	69.45	6.806	0.000	1
1	One	3.28	0.789	65.64	2.370	0.002	2
3	Three	3.26	0.785	65.23	2.207	0.033	3
4	Four	2.70	0.678	53.91	-2.982	0.005	4
2	Two	2.56	0.719	51.23	-4.045	0.000	5
	Total	3.01	0.373	60.16	0.144	0.886	

The table shows that the students face difficulties when learning intonation. However, the best result was found in the first question, for its weight mean is 65.64%. This implies that the students can identify the intonational pattern (rising, falling), but there is a kind of difficulty. Regarding the second question, the weight mean is 51.23% (less

than 60%). This implies that the students found difficulty in identifying the kind of complex intonational pattern (rising-falling, falling-rising). The weight mean of the question three is 65.23% which means the students can hardly underline the syllable of rising pitch. Question four shows serious difficulty at 53.9% when they were required to underline the suitable tonic-syllable. Question five has weight mean of 69.47 which points out the students can explain the two potential meaning, but there is a difficulty in defining the tonic syllable, tone boundaries, and intonational semantic function.

What difficulties do the EFL learners (junior) at IUG, Palestine face while learning intonation in spoken contexts?

To this, the following frequencies of responses for each item in the test were received which were calculated in terms of the mean, standard deviation, weight mean, t-value, and p-value.

Table 5: Results of all questions (Observation Activities)

No	Items	Mean	Standard deviation	Weight mean	t-value	p-value	rank
1	One	3.16	0.486	63.27	2.496	0.016	2
2	Two	3.10	0.663	62.00	1.119	0.268	3
3	Three	2.73	0.530	54.51	-3.840	0.000	4
4	Four	2.51	0.531	50.25	-6.802	0.000	5
5	Five	3.28	0.537	65.60	3.867	0.000	1
	Total	3.01	0.288	58.51	-1.913	0.061	

The table shows that the average mean is 2.93 and the weight mean equals 58.51% which is less than 60% and the absolute value of t-test equals 1.913 which is less than the critical value 2.0 and the p-value equals 0.061 which is greater than 0.05. All these imply that the English major students at IUG have problems of learning intonation at significant level $\alpha = 0.05$

Student's awareness regarding the intonational functions

1- Grammatical function: in the written test, the students could identify the simple intonational pattern (rise, fall), but they did not managed to do that with the

complex pattern. On the other hand, in the spoken test, they were able to recognize the tone group boundaries and underline the syllable of the rising pitch, but they couldn't repeat sentences of intonational patterns (falling, rising, falling-rising, rising-falling).

- 2- Attitudinal and discoursal functions: In the spoken form, the student failed to utter the yes-no by using the intonational pattern, and they couldn't identify the place for the tonic stress after reading the opening sentence.
- 3- Accentual function: when the students listened to the English native speakers by cassette or CD, they asked to replay it again to underline the tonic syllable.
- 4- Focus and/or prominence: The students cannot recognize the stress place and failed to use the intonational pattern to say yes/no.

4.2 Summary of the Findings

The findings confirm that the EFL learners (junior) at IUG, Palestine encounter difficulties while learning the intonational patterns. These difficulties do not have the same weight mean as they vary according to the intonation function and pattern.

The level of difficulties which EFL learners (junior) at IUG, Palestine have while learning intonation in the written context include: the average mean equals 3.01 and the weight mean is 60.16%, which is greater than 60%. Therefore, the English junior students at IUG face various difficulties when learning intonation in the written context at significant level $\alpha = 0.05$

The EFL learners (junior) at IUG, Palestine also have difficulties while learning intonation in the spoken context. The average mean equals 2.3 and the weight mean is 58.51%, which is less than 60%. Therefore, EFL learners (junior) at IUG, Palestine face more difficulties when learning intonation in spoken form at significant level $\alpha = 0.05$. The

students cannot recognize the intonational functions, so their awareness of the intonational functions varies. Students' awareness of the intonational functions in written test is better than their awareness in spoken test. Their awareness of the simple intonation pattern (weight mean, 65.64%) was higher than their awareness of the complex intonation pattern (weight mean 51.23%). The awareness of underlining the word's tone-syllable of rising pitch (weight mean, 65.23%) is higher than their awareness of underlining it in a sentence (weight mean, 53.91). The awareness of the two possible meanings in the written test (weight mean, 69.45%) is higher than in the spoken test (weight mean, 65.6%). The weight mean of identifying the tone group boundaries is 63.27%. The weight mean of the realizing the intonational attitudinal function is 55.20%. The level of students' awareness lies between 50.25% and 69.49%. (The pass level is 60%).

5. Proposed Strategies to Help Overcome these Difficulties while Learning Intonation

- 1- The acoustic analysis should be used to help students to understand the second language features
- 2- The processing instruction on the intonation learning should be used to help students master it.
- 3- It is useful to employ visual aid to introduce stress, rhythm, and tone.
- 4- Using lyrics is an effective method to teach intonation.
- 5- Technology, multimedia, and computer-assisted pronunciation can be used by students to learn intonation.
- 6- Teachers should use effective way to learn intonation rules.
- 7- The students should learn where the native speakers place the nuclear stress and why.

- 8- The students should use role plays to communicate.
- 9- A long exposure to the second language may make the intonation patterns easier.
- 10- The teachers should use graphic representation of the intonation contour, for example, the arrows.
- 11- The best strategy is repetition and imitation.
- 12- The teacher should speak slowly and carefully when teaching tones.
- 13- The teachers may use gestures to clarify rising and falling.
- 14- Students should study contrastive exercises, such as, how to discriminate between the question and statement.
- 15- The students should act out the conversations.
- 16- The student should recognize the stress pattern.
- 17- The teacher should teach students some general rules about intonation and pitch movements.
- 18- The teacher can show the students the connection between the grammatical structure and intonation patterns.
- 19- The teacher should start with the simple intonation pattern before introducing complex pattern.
- 20- The teacher should employ the context when teaching attitudinal intonation.
- 21- The learners should repeat the intonation after a native speaker model.
- 22- The learners should be exposed to the audio material rather than the written materials.
- 23- The teachers should employ the real-life recordings and show the relation between the intonation pattern and the behavior of the speakers.
- 24- Learners prefer the use of computer showing their pitch movements and should be used.

6. Sum Up

To sum up, reflection upon the findings of the research helps to draw following conclusions: EFL learners (junior) at IUG, Palestine have various difficulties in learning intonation, such as, the intonational pattern, underlining the words and sentences tone-syllable of rising pitch, identifying the tone boundaries, realizing the attitudinal intonation function and explaining the two possible meaning of a sentence. The most serious problems for the learners are defining the suitable intonation tone patterns in simple and complex contexts, and explaining the two possible meanings of a sentence in terms of intonation. The learners also find more difficulties in spoken text than the written text when learning the intonational functions. However, there are various techniques and strategies which may help the students learn the intonation, for instance, repetition and imitation, interacting with native speakers, showing the relation between the intonation pattern and intonational functions, and the use of technology. If used seriously, consciously and repetitively, they may go long way in overcoming these problems in intonation.

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